

THE FAIR SHARED CITY APPROACH TO URBAN COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT

OWORONSHOKI, LAGOS

CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION

HOW TO USE THIS BOOKLET

CHAPTER 1

CONTRASTS

CHAPTER 2

THE FAIR SHARED CITY

CHAPTER 3

PLANNING CHECKLIST

CHAPTER 4

BEYOND PLANNING

CREDITS

Fabulous Urban Nigeria Foundation.

FABULOUS URBAN is an urban design, research, and planning firm with a focus on the Global South that was founded in Geneva and is now established in Zurich and Lagos. We take a research-driven urban design approach. We create position statements and background information while also acting as a think tank.

www.fabulousurban.com

Heinrich Böll Foundation.

The Heinrich Böll Foundation Abuja collaborates with activists, thinkers, and networkers in civil society, business, and politics to promote public discussion and action for a socially just and sustainable Nigeria.

ng.boell.org

Project Coordinator:

Adeposi Adeogun

Project Leads:

Monika Umunna, Aro Ismaila

Concept Development:

Fabienne Hoelzel

Lab Facilitators:

Oluwatobi Alaje, Akinbile Naimah, Yewande Morris,
Fagbeiro Philip, Tijani Akhanene

BIBLIOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

This is a publication by Heinrich Böll Stiftung Abuja office and Fabulous Urban Nigeria Foundation.

Date: November 2022

Content and Copy Editor:

Adeposi Adeogun, Fabienne Hoelzel

Photography:

Eve Nnaji, Adeposi Adeogun, Philip Fagbeiro, Tobechukwu Okonkwo

Layout Design:

Esedere Oghenetega

INTRODUCTION

HOW TO USE THIS BOOKLET

This booklet consists of **four** chapters designed to be considered either in sequence or independently of each other. Each objective is closely tied to the following sustainable development goals: **SDG5, SDG9, SDG10, SDG11,** and **SDG17**. The booklet is also designed to engage the user by provoking thought and generating feedback. Urban designers, planners, project managers, design students, researchers, and enthusiasts for just and sustainable urban development will find this guide useful for charting their own futures. The booklet provides QR links to several reports and videos that can be used for case study analyses on gender inclusive planning techniques and strategies. It also includes ample 'whitespace' that can be used for taking notes, critical analysis of points made and making suggestions, all handy for future use.

CONTRASTS

This chapter introduces the Fair Shared City concept in comparison with the main features of the predominant approach to urban planning in sub-Saharan cities. This contrast is showcased using a high-level theoretical analyses of the functioning principles behind African cities.

THE FAIR SHARED CITY

The Fair Shared City project is a direct response to the failure of government and society at large to recognize and include women as key stakeholders in the discourse of urban development. This chapter outlines how the concept was implemented in Oworonshoki, Lagos.

PLANNING CHECKLIST

This chapter synthesises the experiences and lessons from the Fair Shared City project and its theoretical underpinnings into a checklist for adopting a thoroughly inclusive system for urban planning in sub-Saharan cities.

BEYOND PLANNING

Plans are only the first step in achieving a Fair Shared City. Thus, it is critical that the pathway carved beyond inclusive planning remains fair and just. This chapter recommends, through case studies, how to do just that.

CONTRASTS

THE PLANNING PROCESS IN SUB-SAHARAN AFRICAN CITIES TODAY

With African cities growing at the fastest rate in the world, the need to understand how these cities are planned, maintained and preserved for the future has never been more important. Sub-Saharan cities, which will make up a quarter of the world population by 2050¹, need to be understood and better planned for the central role they will play in the world's urban future².

Addressing this would first require an awareness of the unique set of nuances in their evolution and history. For example, Lagos, the largest city in sub-Saharan Africa, has constantly been undergoing a major urban sprawl that can be linked not only to vast rural migration, but also to the agglomeration of small villages into towns, and large towns into the city. Several other cities, such as Cairo and Kinshasa, have also grown in similar ways³.

The urban planning process in sub-Saharan Africa has resulted in the cities we have today, which are unable to evolve and cater to their increasing inhabitants, leading to increased poverty, insecurity, environmental degradation, and scarcity of resources. This process is generally characterised by male dominance, rigidity, exclusivity, and a borrowed identity.

MALE DOMINATED

Regardless of research showing that women occupy only 10 percent of the highest ranked jobs in leading architectural firms, the fact that cities have been planned by men traditionally is most reflected by who thrives in them⁴. As it is the cultural norm in these parts to encourage the domestication of women and her exemption from decision making outside of the home, it is no surprise that the process of urban planning has also been designated to males. Although women make up half of the population and contribute to the social, economic and political welfare of their cities, they aren't a major consideration in the design of the city. This is obvious in cities where the provision, distribution and maintenance of key urban service infrastructure are designed for men yet used mostly by women. Thus, women do not feel safe in poorly lit streets and public spaces and have a harder time connecting and planning their daily travel routes.

RIGID MASTER PLANNING

The influence of colonisation is still obvious in most African cities, long after their independence. One of these effects is the city planning process and policies that are still in play today. Planning tools such as master plans, zoning laws, and urban policies, which are not flawed in themselves, have failed to cater to the needs of the rapidly urbanising region as it evolves. The time, funding, bureaucracy, and resources required for the traditional urban planning process simply don't match up to the reality of these urban areas. As a result, there is a proliferation of incomplete 'mega-projects,' heralding a vision for a future desired by few and unknown to most⁵. The master plans drawn up by a few planners and architects thus have no real meaning to the majority of people who will form their own enclaves and hotspots around it.

EXCLUSIVE & ELITIST

Although a third of Africans live below the poverty line⁶, this reality isn't reflected in the planning policies of most cities. For example, the focus on motorised transport infrastructure in Nigerian cities where an average of 1 person in 60 owns a vehicle⁷, shows that the urban planning process is targeted at the wealthy minority. In an attempt to create the ideal city, the process of urban planning doesn't acknowledge the presence of the poor or poverty in the city, therefore designing for a city that doesn't exist. In cities like Nigeria's capital, Abuja, policies continue to be made that exclude the poorer population, and lead to the destruction of lives and property in a bid to carry out urban plans. The emergence of slums in satellite areas is then unavoidable, leading to even more spatial and environmental challenges.

BORROWED IDENTITY

The effects of globalisation have changed the perception of environmental and spatial values over the years, not only in sub-Saharan Africa, but globally. Today, most major cities look very similar, characterised by glass box towers, manicured boulevards and wide pavements that don't reflect the city's unique identity. The plans and visions for most sub-Saharan cities are more western than authentic, promoting a subjective aesthetic at the cost of functionality, identity, and the reality of day to day living in the city. This repetition is owed primarily to the tools utilised. It is unreasonable to expect truly different outcomes while utilising the same tools. Thus, whenever contemporary African urban designers attempt to produce authentic and vernacular plans, they often fall back into the same categories seen in the global North.

1. Bremner, J., Frost, A., Haub, C., Mather, M., Ringheim, K., & Zuehlke, E. (2010). World population highlights: Key findings from PRB's 2010 world population data sheet. *Population Bulletin*, 65(2), 1-12.

2. *Africapolis*. (n.d.). Africapolis. Retrieved November 3, 2022, from <https://africapolis.org/en/about/beyond-large-cities>

3. Chenal, J. (2016). Capitalizing on Urbanization. *Foresight Africa: top priorities for the continent in 2016*, 59-72.

4. Cobbinah. (2022, January 24). *Why public engagement is key to improving urban planning in Africa*. World Economic Forum. Retrieved from <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2022/01/africa-cities-covid-climate-public-urbanization/>

5. Watson, V. (2020). Digital visualisation as a new driver of urban change in Africa. *Urban Planning*, 5(2), 35-43.

6. Azzari, C., & Signorelli, S. (2020). Climate and poverty in Africa South of the Sahara. *World development*, 125, 104691.

7. Adebola, B. A., Adebayo, O., & Emmanuel, M. A. (2015). Modelling the effect of income and car ownership on recreational trip in Akure, Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Technology*, 4(3), 228-230.

CONTRASTS

THE FAIR SHARED CITY APPROACH TO URBAN PLANNING

This approach is borne out of the unequal relationship people of different genders have with the cities they live in. As the name implies, it advocates for a more equal and positive experience for all in the city and is rooted in social justice, digital equity, spatial justice, and environmental justice. On these principles, the city is planned spatially, economically, and socially, making it more adaptive and people centred. The Fair Shared City approach is inclusive, innovative, people-driven and process-driven.

DEVELOPMENT FOR ALL

Although it commonly appears as a casual cliché without a clear definition in the national debate, 'inclusive growth' is a goal that is supported by all political groups. There is widespread agreement that significant economic and social reform is necessary¹. However, there is no consensus on what this should entail or how it could be accomplished. The Fair Shared City ensures that everyone involved in the decision making process of a place, policy or system is a part of that place or engages with the system. Unlike the current paternalistic urban planning approach in African cities, which is driven and decided by people who often have not even been to the communities they decide for, this approach invites the main users to make decisions concerning their communities, strengthening the sense of ownership and belonging.

ABDUCTIVE THINKING

In place of borrowing ideas, the Fair Shared City planning process ensures that each resulting solution is unique to a community and its problem, never a one size fits all solution. In doing so, it becomes a cradle for innovation in the city. The Fair Shared City also does not subscribe to the dichotomy of problems and solutions, but instead explores the multiplicity of contexts and scenarios of everyday living. This understanding ensures that planners and designers work together with community members to intervene in their communities and co-produce innovation.

PEOPLE DRIVEN

Another characteristic that distinguishes the Fair Shared City approach from the traditional urban planning process is that it is typically carried out without the architect or planner at its core. This does not mean, however, that it is purely a bottom up system of participatory planning by definition. Rather, it graciously empowers the citizen to plan and design. As opposed to separating the roles of user and designer, in the Fair Shared City, the user is a co-designer. By bringing the key community stakeholders to the drawing board, not merely to review or approve previously designed plans but to create the designs they need, the planning process becomes much more meaningful and just². This implies that the infrastructure, spaces and systems developed in this way will not only be owned by community members but will also transform and be transformed by the social capital of that region. Local knowledge and skills necessary for operation and maintenance will also naturally evolve.

PROCESS DRIVEN

While the bulk of process-driven approaches to urban design and planning tend to focus on the technical delivery of services, using big data, smart technology and the Internet of Things to simulate, visualise and transform cities³, cities of the Global South require an even more complex tool which is dialogue. Effective dialogue involves all people actively participating in a way that advances the conversation and encourages positive change in the community, rather than merely sampling the opinions of numerous people on a particular issue. As opposed to rigid master plans or zoning laws, this approach to planning focuses on the dynamics between stakeholders in urban systems and how they connect with one another. The approach embodies this by bringing the actors together to engage in discussions, workshops and focus groups, ideating and collaborating with other experts with varying specialities, in order to come up with interventions to improve the quality of life in their community.

¹ Ameen, R. F. M., Mourshed, M., & Li, H. (2015). A critical review of environmental assessment tools for sustainable urban design. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 55, 110-125.

² Meléndez, J. W., & Parker, B. (2019). Learning in participatory planning processes: Taking advantage of concepts and theories across disciplines. *Planning Theory & Practice*, 20(1), 137-144.

³ Rathore, M. M., Ahmad, A., Paul, A., & Rho, S. (2016). Urban planning and building smart cities based on the internet of things using big data analytics. *Computer networks*, 101, 63-80.

Scan to download digital copy

AN INTERVIEW WITH THE GAMEMAKER

Adeposi ADEOGUN - Project Coordinator

WHAT IS THE IDEA?

The idea is to use a card game to introduce women from low-income communities to the urban planning and decision-making processes.

HOW DID YOU COME UP WITH THE IDEA?

The idea of the game card for urban planning was a merger of three experiences. Firstly, a design studio at the ABK Stuttgart where I co-developed the idea of urban laboratories as decentralised governance structures. Secondly, I entered a design competition where I proposed augmented reality gameplay as a feature of urban living in 2040 (Amsterdam).

Thirdly, the concept for 'The Fair Shared City,' which outlined four pillars for sustainable cities to be Social Justice, Spatial Justice, Environmental Justice, and Digital Equity [[see page 11](#)]. Soon after, I produced the first prototype of the game and presented it to a few friends and colleagues to test out the mechanics in two workshops using Google Jamboard. After receiving sufficient feedback, I produced the graphic design elements of the cards and printed the first copy.

HOW DOES IT WORK?

Through a collaborative and voluntary process of role-playing, participants learn the basics of problem identification, agenda setting, debating, negotiation, ideation, and presentation.

This process involves the use of five cards called the Challenge Card, the Role Card, the Idea Card, the Stakeholder Card and the Fund / Funding System Card. The first way the game is completed/successful is when a playing group lays out all its cards and connects them in a loop using 'logic lines' (a logic line is simply a line explaining the relationship between two cards).

The second way the game is successful is when the group is able to translate its ideas into practical urban interventions.

WHAT IMPACTS CAN IT HAVE?

Because women have largely been ignored and excluded from urban planning structures at all levels, especially at the grassroots level, the majority of them are unaware of the conversations that take place in Community Development Associations. Most women participating in these CDAs have been relegated to the roles of treasurer and secretary, holding no real influence on the decisions made regarding community development. And this is ironic because women are the real drivers behind the informal urban systems, providing access to water, mobility, food, housing, and energy. Therefore, the project will empower women to participate in the urban planning process through either already established structures or new groups made up of fellow gamers. The promotion of the game will also spread this alternative approach to community development across cities facing similar challenges, and successful cases of the game's completion will serve as a basis for further adoption and closing of the infrastructure gap in cities (resolving conflicting rationalities).

WHO IS INVOLVED?

The project involves initiation by an urban designer, planner, architect, or simply anyone with an active interest in urban development. Next, a critical component of the project is the inclusion of women from low-income communities in the city. This is important because these low-income communities form the majority of urban residents in African cities, they occupy the largest shares of the urban extent; and they facilitate about 70 % of the economies of these cities (estimates according to the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development). Subsequently, the women's groups may choose to include other stakeholders to assist in translating the gameplay into urban interventions.

THE FAIR SHARED CITY

The Fair Shared City is an approach that veers away from the current thinking, approaches and instruments for urban development in most sub-Saharan African cities. As opposed to the economic growth-centric focus in these cities, this approach is guided by principles of social justice, spatial justice, environmental justice, and digital equity. At the start of 2022, this approach was tested out in a community located at the heart of Lagos; Oworonshoki. The approach was deployed through quarterly urban laboratories aimed at building the capacity of women to engage in the urban planning process. During these labs, women were given safe spaces to freely discuss the daily realities, develop creative interventions and plan for implementation through collaborative effort.

The first urban lab saw the convergence of over 30 women from different parts of the Oworo community, many of whom were meeting each other for the first time.

Also critical to the functioning of the urban lab were the three lab assistants in charge of facilitating groups, giving technical inputs and offering general support to the event management. This first lab introduced a gamified system for urban planning and decision making using cards.

The second urban lab saw the presence of 27 selected women from the first urban lab, five facilitators, and three coordinators in a full day workshop format event.

Slideshow presentations, introductions and brainstorming sessions were featured in this second phase of the four-part-long series on women's empowerment in urban development. The second lab also involved urban system analyses through focus group discussions and questionnaires.

The third urban lab of the Fair Shared City project was a focused and concise group based discussion to identify the stakeholders to engage and a timeline for the implementation of the selected ideas.

During this lab, the ideas generated from a synthesis of expert opinions and previous lab engagements were presented to the women's groups by the group facilitators and attending group members. Decisions about potential stakeholders and timeline structures were made intermittently after careful consideration within each group. At the end, each group was tasked with developing their chosen ideas into full proposals.

WORKSHOPS

URBAN LAB REVIEW

WORKSHOPS

The review workshops were designed to provide objective feedback to the deliberations and analyses taking place in the labs. The first review took place after the first two labs and brought together professionals from a vast array of specialisations beyond the built environment.

This was in line with the project concept; to develop planning systems devoid of the biases of architects and planners, yet still guided by logically sound methodology. The methodology applied was the system of Abductive Thinking by Jon Kolko¹. This methodology can be summarised as follows; keyword association, concept mapping, pattern identification, and insight combination. During the keyword association stage,

responses from group discussions and questionnaires are presented to the various professional groups using data cards. Each card is then read to the group and interpreted into single or multiple keywords. In the next stage, these keywords are ordered according to their perceived hierarchies, and a concept map is constructed with larger/general words at the top and specific/niche words at the bottom.

In the third stage, logical patterns are identified from the word map, and those patterns are then extracted to form new sentences. These sentences form the basis for insights and combinations; subjective interpretations by professionals in order to generate innovative ideas.

¹. Kolko, J. (2010). Sensemaking and framing: A theoretical reflection on perspective in design synthesis.

see the report

Energy Group

Food Group

Housing Group

Water Group

Mobility Group

Overall Group

The learnings from the unique variants of the methodology initially proposed have influenced our understanding of how to engage with professionals and experts in future workshops. The outputs from the conversations informed the third urban lab, where the women participants were invited to select, combine or refine the ideas presented to them.

Afterwards, they proceeded to develop that idea further with the prospect of meeting relevant stakeholders, setting up meaningful sub-groups, obtaining funding, and rallying support for the implementation of the chosen idea. By deconstructing and reconstructing arguments using this methodology, simple yet obvious gaps in our understanding of challenges in urban systems became evident, and the ideas that closed those gaps became the interventions necessary within the community. The table on page 19 shows some examples of how the challenges of the urban system were redefined as well as the ideas that were synthesised from them.

CHALLENGES IDENTIFIED	ACTIONS PROPOSED
<p>WATER GROUP: 'Clean water no dey'. This simple maxim is used to connote the idea that, despite the fact Oworosnshoki is a community surrounded by the Lagos Lagoon, there is an appalling lack of potable water. As a result, community members have to travel very far (>1 km) to get water.</p> <p>Others have to rely on water cart-pushers who sell to households at exponential rates. Households with boreholes are also unable to use water from the aquifer, because of years of environmental pollution and injustice in other regions of the city.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To install better waste purification systems at borehole stations in the community. Better purification systems may involve a membrane bioreactor or bag and cartridge filters. Community Development Association (stakeholders) should own and maintain a centralized borehole system with regulated pricing. This involves the same technology already employed in community, with the difference being that the funding, maintenance and operation of the boreholes is primarily by the CDAs
<p>FOOD GROUP: The food challenge was conceived in terms of the ability of the many children within the community to access food. Overpopulation and scarcity were also identified as fundamental to understanding the food crisis. Given that the community has limited arable land, and is surrounded by brackish water, residents are unable to grow their own food and resort to buying food from other parts of the city with access to farm produce. Fishing is also a dwindling vocation, in part because more attention is given to the larger adjacent Makoko community.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food sourced locally through vertical gardens and community owned trees. This hybrid idea involves the technology of vertically stacking crops and directly providing nutrients to seedlings using hydroponics. The second component involving community owned tree provides the opportunity for a tree-loving culture in the community and sun-shading. To identify arable land and provide capital for local food production businesses.
<p>MOBILITY GROUP: The mobility challenge is closely tied to access to economic opportunities and public space. There are also no bus routes within the community, and most people have to use okadas on the poorly maintained arterial roads.</p> <p>The community also has a ferry terminal situated on one of its most accessible nodes, yet it only conveys a tiny fraction of its capacity. Additionally, healthcare services are only accessible by walking and okada, which are not the most ideal mobility options for the sick and injured.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To improve accessibility through a non-motorized transport system. This idea recognizes that last mile transport solutions offer the greatest potential in addressing most of the community's socio-economic challenges; leading to cargo bikes and bicycles. Create a hotspot around the ferry station to bring awareness and interest traffic into the community. The multi-functional hotspot will serve as a 'gravity point'; attracting interest and commuters from within and beyond the community to make use of the ferry terminal.
<p>ENERGY GROUP: Energy required for domestic functions poses the most critical challenge for this group. The rising costs of cooking, freezing and lighting are thus at the core of this group's investigative exercise. As a result of the energy challenge, community members are prone to employing creative tactics to use, conserve and manage their energy consumption. One such strategy involves specifically scavenging waste sachets of gin/local spirit. The combustible spirit and the plastic sachet make excellent fire starters for charcoal cooking pots and kilns.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Briquettes as an alternative domestic fuel. Because released carbon is taken directly from the atmosphere rather than being trapped deep in the earth as with coal, biomass briquettes are technically a renewable source of energy and their emissions do not constitute an anthropogenic greenhouse gas. Solar Panels to serve as energy source for freezing services. These energy intensive services are essential for the fishing vocation. Providing these services would reduce the net energy demand per household.
<p>HOUSING GROUP: According to this group, flooding poses the greatest challenge to housing in the community. Thus, the need to reinforce existing houses and build ones with flood resilient capabilities was discussed. However, community members earn very little income and cannot afford sophisticated building technology or infrastructure to prevent flooding. Most building materials used are easily weathered by brackish lagoon water during floods</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To develop a community-based regulation system for building material treatment and construction quality. This research process would ensure standardization. To build the skill of local artisans through training and experimental construction for flood resilience. Pilot housing schemes using sustainable building materials will be used to provide homes, encourage innovative and new construction methods community-wide.

It is all too easy for the built environment professional circles to remain closed up within themselves, thinking from an exceptionalist perspective; thinking as the solution provider. As a result, planning and design professionals in sub-Saharan African cities tend to work separately from the realities of the urban scenarios around them. Professional bodies rarely engage with the urban poor and the larger faction of educational materials provided to younger planners and designers are borne from Western/European standards. In some cases, design schools are taught to outright consider and accept forced evictions as necessary for urban renewal/rejuvenation efforts. Thus, workshops like these serve to bridge that divide in understanding. It fosters professional-community partnership, helping the planners and designers see, talk to, and cooperate with the people they design for.

Involving design thinking at the community level for urban development does not only benefit the professional community, but also ensures that the practices that community stakeholders already engage in are done in a sustainable and efficient manner. The multiplier effect of empowering hundreds, if not thousands, of 'labs' across the city with a process for planning and a guide for designing urban systems has

far more meaningful potential than any single master plan could achieve in the context of rapidly urbanising and densely congested African cities.

The trajectory of the Fair Shared City project is thus that the findings, learnings and proposals are culminated in a presentation at the final review workshop. These presentations summarise the problems identified, the solutions proposed, how the solutions work, and the technologies, stakeholders, and timelines involved. Furthermore, a call to action is issued to the professionals who have been strategically invited because they can offer meaningful contributions to the success of each group's project. With each successful response to the call to action, a new partnership is formed, one that is aimed at innovating and rethinking the format of urban service delivery on a case by case basis.

It is apparent that this approach to urban development involves a chance factor not seen in traditional master planning. This means that there is a probability that partnerships will not be formed and that ideas might run into the ground. Nevertheless, this limitation does not mean that there will be reduced accountability, but rather greater mobility in decision-making and flexibility when things do not go as planned.

The Fourth Urban Lab was an endeavour that broke away from the conventional approach to conducting the urban labs for the Fair Shared City Project. This endeavour required that the facilitators and their group members work more closely with each other and spend more time brainstorming and critiquing/analysing their projects. The second review workshop took on a hybrid format, employing the collaborative efforts of the labs as well as the professional criticism of the workshops.

This spanned three weeks, with lab facilitators convening the women from the groups in remote locations to critically discuss and develop the ideas from the first review workshop and the third lab.

The discussions took advantage of the digital tools, teaching the women to engage more with social media, chat groups, and search engines for the purpose of developing their chosen interventions.

WHAT NEXT?

BEYOND PLANNING

Urban planning theory popular in scholarship is mostly inadequate for aiding our comprehension of and navigation through the complex reality of people living in the Global South. These urban planning theories, which have their roots in traditional British and European notions of what an effective and 'orderly' city should look like, are completely at odds with the 'on the ground' reality of African cities, which have seen rapid poverty growth in the face of underdeveloped and underfunded local government institutions. As a result, urban dwellers create their own 'governance rules' as they go about their daily lives, independent of the authorities, making the informal domain almost impenetrable to state surveillance. The Fair Shared City is a planning strategy that balances these 'rules' with global best practices and strategies. Overall, this strategy increases the likelihood of more planning, more partners, and more action.

INCLUSIVE PLANNING

MORE PARTNERS

MORE ACTION

The problem with planning in Southern cities has to do with the discourse and perception. Those who produce the city on a daily basis, like the women in Owonronshoki, already engage in planning. We need a recognition and understanding of these efforts and then, we can conceptualise a way to do it better. We believe that a rapidly

Although it recognizes the significance of physical urban infrastructure, the Fair Shared City approach to urban development is primarily supportive of the way networks of relationships are set up to increase people's access to opportunities and resources outside of government interventions. As a result, the Fair Shared City requires the constant

Today, the perspectives of low-income residents are still not taken into consideration in urban plans, designs and implementation efforts, which usually fail when governments lack competence and resources. The Fair Shared City approach, as opposed to master planning, does not initially produce spatial plans, instead primarily consists of frameworks

urbanising world needs a wider range of theoretical thinking to interpret the complex and multiple urbanisation processes, one of them being the Fair Shared City approach. We also believe that our understanding of today's cities must be more multifaceted. Thus, in order to develop such a theoretical foundation,

creation of new networks of stakeholders and goes far beyond project implementation. It is through such partnerships that everyone has a fair share of the city. Although the role of the state is reduced, it suggests that it plays the role of a partner as opposed to a driver of development. Further research, pilot programmes and community engagement

and principles that guide stakeholders to transform their communities gradually. It is also crucial that implementation plans are inclusive and participatory; acknowledging the important role women play in utilising and operating essential urban systems. To successfully do this, the established planning system must build capacities of these actors

substantive practice and policy engagements that present the everyday practices of the urban poor need to be regularly conducted. Better planning therefore means a change to an approach that includes women at the center of the planning discourse.

are needed to understand how such innovative partnerships and strategies can be sustained over time and how we can avoid creating redundant parallel spaces that coexist outside of formal institutional structures (although supported by academia and civil-society led initiatives).

to engage meaningfully during the execution phase. This could be through project management, construction, research, and advocacy skills. Therefore, gender equality is seen throughout the entire planning life-cycle; from inception to implementation.

OWORONSHOKI, LAGOS

**FABULOUS
URBAN**
NIGERIA FOUNDATION

■■■ HEINRICH BÖLL STIFTUNG
ABUJA
Nigeria